

NATIONAL AND CULTURAL FEATURES OF COMPOSING NEGATIVE SENTENCES IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this paper is to look at the category of negation from what might be considered as the periphery of grammar. In this periphery, we find patterns which are less general or well-known than constructions like the passive or the imperative, but which are no less part of the grammatical competence of speakers.

Key words: Negation, grammar operation, to express a preposition, negation stereotypes.

Negation is a grammatical operation, typically effectuated by not, that reverses the polarity of an implicitly understood background clause, thus producing a clause that expresses a proposition which is semantically the opposite of the proposition expressed by the background clause. The marginal patterns discussed here are special because of certain idiosyncratic syntactic and semantic properties, and they are furthermore interesting with respect to negation. I will first introduce the form and concept of negation by means of a series of stereotypically negative clauses: detention lines written on a blackboard. A discussion of them will lead me to venture a general definition of negation. I will then propose three simplistic views of negation, which in the subsequent sections will be argued to be impossible to be upheld. Secondly I devoted to the correlative comparative construction I will show that negation of the second part of this pattern is only possible under certain conditions, thus rejecting the view that adding a negator is an easy operation that can be applied to any positive clause. Additionally, I will more briefly address conditionals of the. This pattern proves wrong the view that negation is an aspect of meaning that is added to pre-existing propositions, and that all negative sentence types must therefore have a corresponding positive version. deals with the so-called constant polarity tag. I will argue that this term is somewhat unfortunate, since we can observe that a similar antagonistic meaning tends to be expressed by a reversed polarity tag after a negative anchor. English seems to be in the process of developing a rule by which antagonistic tags keep their positive polarity constant, irrespective of the polarity of their anchor. This kind of tag, then, shows that there are constructions

that do not allow to be made negative, again rejecting the more simplistic view to the contrary.

Proposing a definition of negation is not the central aim of this paper, though. On the contrary, I want to say what negation is not—but not without at least trying to state what negation is, as I did. I do not think that these “negation-indifferent” patterns seriously undermine the general definition of negation attempted in sections above. Although it is true that for these cases, adding a negator fails to result in a semantically opposite proposition (if indeed a tag can be said to express a proposition at all), it is clear that the remarkable property of resisting semantic change under a polarity reversal is construction-specific. In any case, these sentences again show that negation is not such a simple operation, contra the first claims, in that its use and interpretation may turn out special in certain constructions. Furthermore, although after a negative anchor, the tag we have been considering in this section may allow both a positive and, for some speakers, a negative version. A positive version is the only choice we have after a positive anchor e.g. So you’re too good for me, aren't you? Consequently, if we consider the tag itself to be a clause, then the second claim saying that each positive clause has a negative counterpart does not hold true for this antagonistic tag. Nor indeed do the second claim and the third claim Together saying that each clause has both a positive and a negative version hold true for the ordinary reversal tag. For example:

It’s rather cold, isn't it? You won’t tell anyone, won't you?.

The older they get, the cuter they are.

The more vegetables I eat, the worse my gastric problems get.

That’ll teach you not to tease the alligators.

I wonder whether we can't find some time to shoot pool this evening.

You shouldn’t play with the alligators, I don’t think.

I couldn’t care less about monster trucks.

The harder we try, the less we achieve.

This pattern evokes paired scales, for example age and cute. Where I discuss the following patterns:

Otto is a person who I think’s ready for such a challenge.

Otto is a person who I don’t think’s ready for such a challenge.

Otto is a person who’s not ready for such a challenge, I don’t think.

In the first sentence, the relative clause has positive polarity; in the second sentence, with an added negator, it has negative polarity; in the third sentence, it still has negative polarity, despite the fact that there is one more negator. The

tagged negative think-clause here does not cancel the negative polarity of the relative clause, but, as it were, merely copies its polarity.

The combination conveys the idea that movement along the one scale correlates with proportional or otherwise corresponding movement along the other. The correlation need not be positive: (4c) refers to an inverse correlation between change on an effort scale and change on a success scale. The construction can be closely paraphrased by means of *as*: “As they get older, they get correspondingly cuter.” A conditional interpretation also often holds

There does not seem to be any semantic difference between the negative and the positive version of the tag under discussion after a negative anchor—the only difference is stylistic, in that the latter probably sounds rather archaic and is (therefore) not acceptable for all speakers of English. Disregarding this stylistic difference, this tag may be counted among “a handful of English constructions. This means that ‘constant polarity tag’ is something of a misnomer. To the extent that speakers prefer to use a positive tag even after a negative anchor, I offer the term ‘constant positive polarity tag’ as a more adequate though somewhat clumsy alternative: the polarity of the tag under discussion here remains positive and is therefore, in a sense, constant, irrespective of the polarity of its anchor.

CONCLUSION

I hypothesize that there is, or has been, a grammatical shift in the English language from ‘constant polarity tags’ to ‘constant positive polarity tags.’ It is reasonable to assume that positive anchors have always outnumbered negative ones, so that the majority of the actual tags of the relevant kind have always been positive. This way, the positive form of the tag has had more opportunity to become entrenched and fossilized. Because the tag under consideration always reacts to something the interlocutor has just said we can expect the anchor to be frequently elliptical. This provides us with an easy way to collect and compare tags. Full details of this evolution await further research, but the following two examples seem to be reversion in which the main clause precedes the subordinate clause, and in which the comparative phrase in the main clause appears in its canonical position and is not generally introduced.

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